

Determinant Factors of Modern Contraceptive Prevalence Among Fertile-Age Couples (Fac)

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the influence of predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing factors on the prevalence of modern contraceptive use among couples of reproductive age (CRA) in Gorontalo Province. A quantitative method using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was employed to identify the relationships among latent variables. The results show that predisposing factors, including knowledge, attitudes, and socio-cultural aspects, have a dominant influence on the prevalence of modern contraception (path coefficient 0.541). Individual attitudes were found to be the most significant indicator in this construct. Enabling factors, such as facilities and resources, have a moderate influence (path coefficient 0.245), indicating that the availability of infrastructure must be accompanied by changes in societal behavior. Reinforcing factors, such as family support and service provider attitudes, have a significant influence (path coefficient 0.301), emphasizing the importance of social support and service quality. In conclusion, the success of modern contraceptive programs in Gorontalo Province requires improvements in knowledge, attitude changes, and the adaptation of cultural norms. Additionally, adequate provision of facilities and social support should be integral to strategies aimed at increasing the prevalence of modern contraceptive use.

Keywords: Modern Contraception, Couples of Reproductive Age, Predisposing Factors, Enabling Factors, Reinforcing Factors.

INTRODUCTION

The total fertility rate (TFR) in Indonesia has shown a gradual decline from 5.61 in 1971 to 2.18 in 2020, reflecting successful family planning programs. However, the prevalence of modern contraceptive use (mCPR) remains uneven across regions, including Gorontalo Province. Bone Bolango and Gorontalo City exhibit lower mCPR rates compared to other districts. Barriers include socio-cultural norms, misinformation about contraceptive safety, and limited access to services.

Family planning programs in Indonesia aim to create "quality families" by managing population growth and improving health and well-being. The National Population and Family Planning Board (BKKBN) has set ambitious targets to reduce TFR to 2.1 and increase the mCPR to 64.99% by 2024. Despite these efforts, disparities persist, particularly in rural and socio-culturally diverse areas like Gorontalo Province. Gorontalo's mCPR of 61.2% in 2023 remains below the national target, with Bone Bolango and Gorontalo City reporting the lowest rates in the region.

Key challenges include cultural resistance to contraception, reliance on traditional methods, and a lack of accessible and reliable information. Additionally, logistical issues such as inadequate healthcare facilities and limited availability of modern contraceptive methods exacerbate the problem (Christie & Budiantara, 2015). These barriers highlight the need for comprehensive strategies that integrate education, accessibility, and community engagement (Kusuma Dewi & Arka, 2021).

The history of family planning in Indonesia demonstrates the interplay of sociocultural, economic, and policy factors (Yainahu and Marsisno, 2021). Initially introduced in the late 1960s, the family planning program gained momentum with support from international organizations and a strong government commitment. Over the decades, contraceptive prevalence increased significantly, but progress has slowed in recent years due to persistent inequities in access and cultural resistance, particularly in less urbanized regions like Gorontalo. Cultural values in Gorontalo Province often emphasize large families as a source of social and economic security. This preference is deeply rooted in traditional beliefs and is further reinforced by limited awareness about the benefits of modern contraceptives. Many couples rely on traditional methods, which are often less effective, due to misconceptions about modern contraceptives causing infertility or other health complications. Addressing these misconceptions is crucial for increasing mCPR.

Religious beliefs also play a significant role in shaping attitudes toward contraception in Gorontalo. While Islamic teachings generally permit family planning under specific conditions, varying interpretations among religious leaders can lead to confusion and resistance. Engaging religious leaders in advocacy efforts can help align family planning initiatives with local values and increase community acceptance (Yainahu & Marsisno, 2021). Economic factors further compound the challenges of family planning in Gorontalo Province. Limited financial resources restrict access to healthcare services, including family planning. Although government programs provide free contraceptives, logistical challenges often hinder their distribution, particularly in remote areas (Alifia, 2018). Strengthening the supply chain and ensuring the availability of contraceptives at all healthcare facilities is essential for improving access. Education and awareness campaigns play a pivotal role in overcoming barriers to contraceptive use. However, these efforts must be tailored to the local context to address the specific needs and concerns of the community. Interactive approaches, such as peer education and community discussions, have proven effective in similar settings and could be adapted for Gorontalo Province.

This study aims to analyze the determinants of mCPR in Gorontalo Province, focusing on predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing factors. By identifying these influences, the research provides evidence-based recommendations to improve contraceptive use and support family planning objectives in the region. The findings can inform targeted interventions that address cultural, economic, and systemic barriers, ultimately contributing to the achievement of national family planning goals.

METHOD

This study was conducted in districts within Bone Bolango Regency and Gorontalo City. The research will take place over three months, from August to October 2024.

Type of Research

This study is an observational analytic research, which examines the relationship between two or more variables without any intervention on the research subjects. The study employs an analytical survey method with a cross-sectional approach, conducting observations or measurements of variables at a single point in time.

Population and Sample

The sampling technique used in this study is Purposive Sampling, which involves selecting samples based on specific considerations, such as the characteristics of a population(Assalis, 2015). The population in this study consists of mothers in Fertile-Age Couples (FAC) at Kabila Health Center in Bone Bolango Regency, totaling 3,389, and at Central City Health Center in Gorontalo City, totaling 3,209. The sample size for this study was determined using the Lemeshow(Tampubolon et al., 2019). The population comprised 6,598 CRA from Bone Bolango and Gorontalo City. A total of 340 respondents were selected using purposive sampling based on criteria such as residency, age, and willingness to participate.

Data Collection

Primary data were collected using validated questionnaires measuring knowledge, attitudes, socio-cultural factors, facility accessibility, family support, and provider attitudes. The instrument or tool used for data collection in this study is a questionnaire. A questionnaire is a data collection method conducted by providing a set of written questions or statements to respondents (Rahman, 2019). The questionnaire in this study contains questions related to the knowledge and socio-cultural environmental conditions of FAC mothers regarding the use of contraceptives. Secondary data were sourced from local health departments.

Data Analysis and Processing

Data analysis in this study employs SEM (Structural Equation Modeling). SEM is a second-generation multivariate analysis technique that allows researchers to examine complex relationships between variables, both recursive and non-recursive, to obtain a comprehensive representation of a statistical model(Suharto, 2016). SEM was employed to examine relationships between latent variables. Model validity and reliability were assessed using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability

RESULT

This study was conducted in Gorontalo Province, specifically in Bone Bolango Regency and Gorontalo City. The selection of these locations was based on the prevalence rate of modern contraceptive use (mCPR). Most respondents were aged 21-35 years, married, and employed. Educational attainment varied, with higher education levels positively correlating with contraceptive use. When including a table in the paper, please select an open table (only use horizontal lines). Place the table in the middle of the page with the title on top left. Based on the questionnaire results, the following data were obtained

Figure 1. Results of SEM Analysis on the Influence of Determinant Factors on the Prevalence Rate of Modern Contraceptive Use Among Fertile-Age Couples

. Table 1. Results of Path Coefficient Analysis and Total Effect)

Determinant Factors	Prevalence Rate
Reinforcing Factors	0.301
Supporting Factors	0.245
Predisposing Factors	0.541

In Table 1, Predisposing Factors Significant impact on mCPR (path coefficient 0.541). Indicators such as knowledge (0.747) and attitudes (0.916) were dominant contributors. Enabling Factors Moderate influence (0.245). Facility accessibility (0.573) and resource availability (0.545) were key. Reinforcing Factors Notable effect (0.301). Family support (0.546) and provider attitudes (0.525) emerged as critical.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight several critical factors influencing the prevalence of modern contraceptive use among couples of reproductive age in Gorontalo Province. The discussion is organized based on the key themes of predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing factors identified through the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis.

Predisposing factors, such as knowledge and attitudes, emerged as the most significant determinants of mCPR, with a path coefficient of 0.541. Knowledge of modern contraceptive methods plays a crucial role in shaping positive attitudes and reducing misconceptions. Respondents with higher levels of education were more likely to have accurate information and favorable attitudes toward contraceptive use. Misconceptions, regarding side effects and safety, remain prevalent among less-educated populations. This aligns with previous educational studies emphasizing the need for targeted campaigns to address these gaps. Attitudes toward contraception are deeply influenced by socio-cultural norms. In Gorontalo Province, traditional beliefs and religious considerations significantly impact decision-making regarding family planning. Some respondents expressed reluctance to use modern contraceptives due to perceived conflicts with cultural or religious values. Addressing these barriers requires culturally sensitive interventions that involve community leaders and religious authorities to promote the compatibility of modern contraception with local values. These results are consistent with the theory that changes in individual behavior are strongly influenced by predisposing factors, particularly in the context of community-based interventions. According to the theory of demographic transition, an increase in education levels and public awareness (knowledge) is one of the key factors influencing population behavior changes, including the reduction of prevalence rates for certain issues (eg, health or social prevalence). A more adaptive societal attitude toward change can accelerate social transitions toward lower prevalence rates (Fayon & Marsisno, 2019). Additionally, socio-cultural factors play a crucial role in shaping societal norms and behaviors. According to Parsons' social system theory, cultural elements are one of the primary subsystems influencing societal functions (Koloay et al., 2023). Certain social norms, such as traditions or beliefs, may contribute to prevalence if those norms are not aligned with modern interventions. Therefore, a culturally-based approach is needed to transform norms that are resistant to change

Enabling factors, including accessibility to facilities and availability of resources, had a moderate influence on mCPR, with a path coefficient of 0.245. Accessibility to healthcare facilities is a critical determinant of contraceptive use. Respondents living in remote areas reported limited access to clinics and family planning services. The availability of contraceptive methods in healthcare facilities is also varied, with some clinics experiencing stock-outs of certain methods, further discouraging potential users. Improving infrastructure and logistics is essential to ensure consistent availability of contraceptives. Mobile health

clinics and outreach programs can bridge the gap in underserved areas. Additionally, training healthcare providers to deliver high-quality, client-centered services can enhance trust and satisfaction among users, ultimately increasing uptake. This can be linked to the theory of carrying capacity in population studies. According to this theory, a population requires adequate infrastructure to sustain its livelihood. The insufficiency of facilities, such as health or education services, can exacerbate the prevalence of social or health issues. The analysis results indicate that while the provision of adequate facilities is essential, its impact will not be optimal without behavioral changes driven by predisposing factors. Within the framework of Human Ecology Theory, the distribution and availability of resources influence the balance between population and environment. Limited access to quality resources, such as healthcare services or economic resources, can affect the prevalence of issues in a region (Syamsul et al., 2020).

Reinforcing factors, such as family support and provider attitudes, also played a significant role, with a path coefficient of 0.301. Family dynamics, particularly spousal communication, were identified as critical in influencing contraceptive decisions. Couples who openly discussed family planning were more likely to adopt modern contraceptive methods. Conversely, lack of communication often leads to reliance on traditional methods or non-use. Provider attitudes were another important aspect of reinforcing factors. Respondents who reported positive interactions with healthcare providers were more likely to trust and utilize modern contraceptive methods. Providers who exhibited empathy, professionalism, and cultural sensitivity significantly influenced users' perceptions of family planning services. Conversely, negative experiences, such as judgmental attitudes or lack of confidentiality, deter respondents from seeking services. Based on Social Network Theory, support from family, community, and formal institutions can enhance societal adaptability to change, especially when addressing complex issues (Anggrainy et al., 2022). In this context, consistent support contributes to strengthening both individual and collective capacities in reducing the prevalence of modern contraceptive use.

The multifaceted nature of factors influencing mCPR underscores the need for integrated approaches to improve contraceptive use. Educational interventions should focus on addressing knowledge gaps and reshaping attitudes through community-based campaigns. These campaigns should involve trusted figures, such as religious leaders and local influencers, to ensure cultural relevance and acceptance. From an operational perspective, strengthening healthcare infrastructure and supply chains is critical to addressing enabling factors. Policies should prioritize the allocation of resources to underserved areas and support mobile clinics to reach remote populations. Additionally, training program providers should emphasize the importance of client-centered care and cultural competence. Social interventions targeting reinforcing factors should aim to foster open communication within families and communities. Spousal communication can be promoted through couple-focused counseling sessions, while community engagement activities can address broader social norms and stigma associated with modern contraception.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Predisposing factors significantly influence mCPR, with attitudes and knowledge being primary contributors. Enabling and reinforcing factors also play essential roles in shaping contraceptive behavior. The findings of this study align with Indonesia's national goals of increasing mCPR to 64.99% by 2024 and achieving a total fertility rate of 2.1. However, achieving these targets in regions like Gorontalo Province requires tailored strategies that address local barriers and leverage community strengths. Collaboration between government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and community leaders is essential to implement effective interventions and monitor progress.

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